

Prepositions in English language and their usage

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Abstract

Prepositions are words that help us link nouns, pronouns, and phrases to other words within a sentence. They are one of the most commonly used parts of speech in English and are often essential for crafting an effective and accurate sentence.

Prepositions are short words (on, in, to) that usually stand in front of nouns (sometimes also in front of gerund verbs).

Even advanced learners of English find prepositions difficult, as a 1:1 translation is usually not possible. One preposition in your native language might have several translations depending on the situation.

Key words: interesting, obvious, particular, realization, generous. Satellite, rivalry, curiosity, vital

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Отрывок

Предлоги — это слова, которые помогают нам связывать существительные, местоимения и фразы с другими словами в предложении. Они являются одной из наиболее часто используемых частей речи в английском языке и часто необходимы для составления эффективного и точного предложения. Предлоги — это короткие слова (on, in, to), которые обычно стоят перед существительными (иногда также перед герундийными глаголами). Даже продвинутым игрокам, изучающим английский язык, предлоги кажутся трудными, поскольку перевод 1:1 обычно невозможен. Один предлог на вашем родном языке может иметь несколько переводов в зависимости от ситуации.

Ключевые слова: интересный, очевидный, конкретный, реализация, щедрый. Спутник, соперничество, любопытство, жизненно важное значение

What Is a Preposition?

A preposition is a short word that is employed in sentences to show the relationship nouns, pronouns or phrases have with other parts within the respective sentences. Prepositions are normally found positioned in the latter part of the sentence, but before a noun or pronoun.

Definition of a Preposition

A preposition is defined as “a word that connects a noun, a noun phrase, or a pronoun to another word, esp. to a verb, another noun, or an adjective”, according to the Cambridge Dictionary. The Oxford Learner’s Dictionary says that a preposition is “a word or group of words, such as in, from, to, out of and on behalf of, used before a noun or pronoun to show place, position, time or method.”

The Collins Dictionary defines a preposition as “a word such as ‘by’, ‘for’, ‘into’, or ‘with’ which usually has a noun group as its object.” The Merriam Webster Dictionary provides a slightly different definition. According to it, a preposition is defined as “a function word that typically combines with a noun phrase to form a phrase which usually expresses a modification or predication.”

Uses of Prepositions

Prepositions are seen to show some key characteristics and perform some vital functions when used in sentences. Let us look at the various uses of prepositions in English.

They are used to show the direction of something.

They can refer to the time of something happening.

They can be used to denote the position or location of an object in the sentence.

They are also used to represent spatial relationships.

Prepositional phrases, in particular, can be used to do all of these when used in sentences.

Types of Prepositions

Based on the different uses and functions of prepositions, they can be divided into four main types. They are as follows:

Prepositions of Time – used to show when something is happening.

For example:

We will be meeting on Friday.

The supermarket will be closed from 9 p.m. to 9 a.m.

Can you come after some time?

We have been asked to work from home until the end of May.

The whole country was asked to stay home during the pandemic to ensure safety and well-being.

Prepositions of Place – indicate the place or position of something.

For example:

I have kept the book I borrowed from you on the table.

Henry hid behind the door.

The dog jumped over the fence.

Can you place the red roses in between the white daisies?

He was waiting in front of the EB office.

Prepositions of Direction – used to denote the direction in which something travels or moves.

For example:

The girl ran toward her father the moment she saw him.

Jerry jumped into the river to help his sister.

Veena passed the book to Priya.

When will Salvia be returning from London?

Neena lives across the street.

Prepositions of Location – employed to denote the location of a particular object.

For example:

Kenny would be staying at his cousin's place for the weekend.

Make sure you keep all the toys back in its place after you play.

I lay on the floor for a really long time.

Prepositions of Spatial Relationship – used to denote an object's movement away from the source and towards a source.

For example:

Navya sat leaning against the wall.

The circus was stationed opposite the children's park.

Lakshmi sat beneath the trees.

Shankar sat beside the stairs.

We spent the evening walking around the lake.

Prepositional Phrase – a combination of a preposition and a noun (the object it is affecting).

For example:

See to it that you reach the venue on time.

The medicines you asked for are out of stock.

Why don't we try taking classes outside for a change.

Make sure you fill in all the forms at once.

Salmaan was able to finish it only with the help of his friends.

Examples of Prepositions Used in Sentences

To know how exactly prepositions can be used in sentences, check out the following sentences.

I will be going to church in the morning.

She placed the plates on the dining table.

Baskar found the cat hiding under the bed.

Will you be with Raimy or Mazeeka?

I love sitting on the beach at night.

Rachel met Phoebe by the lake.

Finn stood opposite Lisa.

The grocery store is right in front of the bus stop.

My brother climbed onto the roof.

It feels great to sit beneath the trees and read.

Now that you know what prepositions are and how they are used in sentences, try working out preposition exercises, preposition of time exercises, preposition exercises for class 10, preposition exercises for class 7 and preposition exercises for class 8.

List of Most Popular Prepositions for Everyday Communication

Given below is an extensive list of prepositions that you can make use of in your daily communication.

Examples of Prepositions

On	At	In	Over
Around	Through	Opposite to	In front of
Behind	Beneath	Beside	Above
Below	Under	Underneath	Down
Up	Out	With	Into
Onto	Across	After	Before
Near	Among	Along	Between
Toward	Away	From	To
Next to	By	Until	About

Commonly Confused Prepositions

With the huge number of prepositions in the English language, it almost seems impossible to have no confusion at all. Here is a list of prepositions that cause confusion among the users of the language.

In/On/At

These three prepositions can be used to depict both time and position. Take a look at the table below to have a better understanding of how it works.

Prepositions of Place

In	On	At
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Can be used to show general locations like neighbourhoods, cities, countries and places with a boundary	Can be used to refer to more specific locations like streets, avenues, islands, surfaces and large vehicles	Can be used to refer to very specific locations
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For example: I live in India.

We will be staying in a hotel tonight.

For example: Latha stays on the fourth floor.

The book you are looking for is on the rack.

For example: You can find us at the park.

She is at home now.

In the company of

For example: Glint went to Chennai with his friends.

A given time or not later than

For example: See that you reach the exam hall by 8:30 a.m.

In addition to

For example: would you like to have tea with breakfast?

Denotes the doer of the action mentioned in a sentence

For example: The poem was written by my brother.

By means of

For example: I cut my birthday cake with a fruit knife.

Frequently Asked Questions on Prepositions in English

Q1

What is a preposition?

A preposition is a short word that is employed in sentences to show the relationship of nouns, pronouns or phrases with other parts within the respective sentences. Prepositions are normally found positioned in the latter part of the sentence.

Q2

What is the definition of a preposition?

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Q3

What are the different types of prepositions?

Prepositions can be divided into different types by categorising them according to their functions. The different types of prepositions are:

some examples of prepositions.

In, on, at, through, across, above, over, up, down, to, with, by, beside, beneath, in front of, between, among, etc. are some examples of prepositions.

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Use "&" before the final author.

Four to seven authors

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